

→ Why I retracted the Bitcoin Guide, despite its success.

MESS 0034

MIMS 2.6X - Proof of Stake (PoS) as part of the POS takeover; digital evidence of the theft of the People's Money by the financial power structure.

It never had to do with saving electricity... it was a scam and theft, pure and simple. Get out of PoS and stay out if you hadn't. Write your Congressman or Parliamentarian.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Why the author is so angry

Cryptocurrency - Bitcoin - and blockchain was a once in a lifetime opportunity for tremendous wealth. The author had a chance, and passed it up. Fine. Now, this opportunity was still pretty good in 2019-2021, however, pretty soon there was a bifurcation of Ethereum, and a change to the algorithm. It seemed like a good opportunity, given it would limit the total amount of new ETH. However, the net result, was that this favored "the big guys" and the plans of the New World Order, and of China and the Federal Reserve, combined

with the actions of POS Supreme (and lap-dog), PM Justin Trudeau with regards to the Canadian fascist shit-show lockdown.

Meanwhile, the algorithms that were used to set up Proof of Stake, and the APR, has really drained investors, and created the conditions of Ponzi Schemes. The lure: massive 'returns' which are nothing more than the influx of money from other investors. But in a bear market, there is tremendous shrinkage and pressure to steal the initial investors, etc.

Even Pancake Swap, which was one of the programs suggested by the author in the "howto" product which was craftily made, has proven to be disappointing in its output. If the token price shrinks faster than the APR, the net result is, ultimately, loss. And the way that crypto has tremendous anti-bullish upside for "Whales" that choose to manipulate the market in "smash n grab" planned scenarios and disassembling investors... well there doesn't seem to be reasons to advise commoners to invest in crypto. For starters, it's difficult to use, and they keep altering the wallet features and conditions.

Then there is the FTX bankruptcy and series of bankruptcies

References

- 1.